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Post Germination Desiccation Tolerance as the Marker of Drought Tolerance in Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.)

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Abstract

Desiccation tolerance (DT) withstands extreme dehydration (90-95% water loss). Post-germination DT is one of three types of DT known to be present in angiosperms. Wheat possesses post-germination DT. Present study found post-germination DT superior in drought tolerant cultivar than drought susceptible cultivar. Further investigation demonstrated that grades of phenolics, lignin, anthocyanins, gamma-amino butyric acid (GABA), proline, sugars and starch and activities of guaiacol peroxidase, glutathione peroxidase, sucrose phosphate synthase, sucrose synthase, and amylases were linked to the post-germination-DT of drought tolerant compared to drought susceptible cultivar. Results concluded that post-germination DT can be the marker of drought tolerance in wheat. Antioxidants, proline, sugars, and GABA may be the chief players involved in post-germination DT in wheat.

Keywords: Wheat; Desiccation; Tolerance; Gamma-amino butyric acid; Glutathione; Peroxidase; Starch; Sucrose synthase

Introduction

Desiccation tolerance (DT) is the ability of living cells to deal with water loss below 0.1 g H₂O g⁻¹ dry weight and survive the re-hydration process without permanent damage (Gechev et al., 2021). Three types of DT are known to be present in angiosperms, vegetative DT, seed DT and post-germination DT. Vegetative DT is seen in resurrection plants, and it remains throughout their life cycle. Seed-DT is acquired during seed maturation however lost during seed germination (Dekkers et al., 2015). Post-germination DT is the revival of DT during germination if seedlings get exposed to environmental stress, however post-germination DT remains within a time window (like 2-3 days after germination) and stress treatment given after this time window cannot induce DT (Maia et al., 2011). Understanding of DT is important as it can be used to build drought tolerance in plants and to build DT in recalcitrant (desiccation-intolerant) seeds of economically important crops, and it can also be applied to enhance the storage lives of biomaterials like somatic embryos, artificial seeds, germplasm, eukaryotic cells, blood cells, tissues, biomolecules or vaccines, etc. (Dekkers et al., 2015).

Antioxidant activity is a crucial component of DT. Unique antioxidants may be involved under desiccation and subsequent rehydration (Veljovic-Jovanovic et al., 2008) however antioxidants are less studied under desiccation compared to other stresses in plants. Gamma-amino butyric acid (GABA) acts as a signaling molecule and activates antioxidant defense and GABA also has metabolic roles under stresses (Seifikalhor et al., 2019). Only a few reports have linked GABA with dehydration. In *Arabidopsis thaliana*, GABA hyperaccumulated in seeds during seed maturation (Fait et al., 2011). GABA accumulated in the embryo and endosperm of green coffee beans (*Coffea arabica* L.) during drying (Kramer et al., 2010). GABA and proline enhanced in radish roots (daikon)

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upon sun drying (Kobayashi et al., 2021). However, GABA has not been well-studied under desiccation or dehydration in plants. Sugars act as osmolytes and stabilize membrane structures and help in glassy state formation during desiccation, and during rehydration, sugars may provide carbon skeletons for the return of growth and metabolism (Dekkers et al., 2015; Gechev et al., 2021). However, the role of carbohydrates under desiccation has not been well studied in plants.

The present study analyzed antioxidants, GABA and carbohydrates under post-germination desiccation and subsequent rehydration in wheat. Analysis has been performed in wheat cultivars with varying degrees of drought tolerance.

Material and methods

Plant material

Plant material was adapted (Maia et al., 2011) and described (Kour and Zhawar, 2018a, b). Six bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) cultivars C306, Dharwad Dry, PBW660, Sunstar and PBW644 (all five were drought tolerant) and PBW343 (drought susceptible) were used in analysis. Two-day old seedlings were exposed to desiccation for 7 days and subsequently rehydrated for the next 7 days. The experiment was performed under continuous light in BOD incubator at 25°C. Seedlings were analyzed at pre-desiccated, desiccated, and rehydrated stages.

Measurements of biochemical contents

Malondialdehyde (MDA) was estimated by the method described (Kour and Zhawar, 2018a), and the amount was calculated using molar extinction coefficient of MDA of 155 mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Protein carbonyls were estimated by the method described (Kour and Zhawar, 2018b) and calculated using extinction coefficient of hydrazones of 22, 000 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Lignin was estimated by protocol followed (Kaur and Zhawar, 2021) and content was calculated by using lignin standard (5–50 µg). Flavonoids and phenolics were estimated by protocols described (Kaur and Zhawar, 2021). Standard curves of gallic acid (2–15 µg) and rutin (25–100 µg) were used in calculating the amounts of flavonoids and phenolics respectively. Anthocyanin was estimated by method derived (Mancinelli, 1984). Contents were expressed in absorbance per g DW. Reduced glutathione (GSH) and oxidized glutathione (GSSG) were measured by the method described (Kaur et al., 2014) and amounts were calculated by running standard of GSH. GABA was estimated by the method mentioned (Kaur et al., 2021). The amount was calculated using standard GABA (250-1000 nmol). Proline was estimated by ninhydrin-based method and mentioned (Kaur et al., 2021). The amount was calculated by running proline standard (0.05–0.5 µmol). Sugar and starch were estimated as suggested (Kaur and Zhawar, 2021). Methanol (80%) extract was used for sugar measurements, while dried residue for starch estimation. Glucose was estimated by glucose oxidase and peroxidase-based method. Sucrose was estimated by the same method as glucose but after enzymatic hydrolysis by using commercial invertase. Fructose was estimated by resorcinol-based method. Diluted perchloric acid was used to hydrolyze starch to glucose, and total sugar was estimated by anthrone method, and the value was multiplied by 0.9 to get starch value.

Measurements of enzymatic activities

Peroxidases (POX) and polyphenol oxidases (PPO) were measured as described (Kaur and Zhawar, 2021). Enzymes were commonly extracted in potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0). POX was assayed using guaiacol and H₂O₂ as substrates and activity was calculated using molar extinction coefficient of tetraguaiacol of 26.6 mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹. PPO was assayed using catechol for change in absorbance at 420 nm and the activity was expressed in absorbance units where one PPO unit is defined as the change in absorbance of one in one hour.

Glutathione peroxidases (GPX) and glutathione-S-transferase (GST) were measured (Kaur et al., 2014). These were commonly extracted in phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) supplemented with EDTA and PVP. GPX was assayed using tertiary-butyl hydroperoxide, reduced glutathione, NADPH and glutathione reductase, and read for disappearance of NADPH at 340 nm. The molar extinction coefficient of NADPH (6.22 mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹) was used in calculation. GST was measured by using reduced glutathione and CDNB (1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene) as substrates and appearance of conjugated-CDNB (CDNB-SG) at 340 nm was noted. Molar extinction coefficient of CDNB-SG (9.6 mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹) was used in calculation.

Glutamate decarboxylase (GAD) and diamine oxidase (DAO) were estimated as mentioned (Kaur et al., 2021). GAD was assayed with glutamate as substrate and GABA formed as product was estimated and calculated by using standard GABA. DAO was assayed with putrescine as its substrate and then product formed was estimated by ninhydrin-based reagent and read at 510 nm. One DAO unit is defined as the change of absorbance of one in one hour.

All enzymes of carbohydrate metabolism were commonly extracted in HEPES-NaOH buffer (pH 7.5) supplemented with EDTA, DTT, MgCl₂, PMSF, PVP and glycerol. Granule bound fraction and soluble fractions were separated as described before (Aggarwal et al., 2024). Enzyme extract from soluble fractions was used in the estimation of all enzymes other than granule bound starch synthase (GBSS) for which granule bound fraction was used. Invertases (INV) were assayed (Kaur and Zhawar, 2021) by using sucrose as substrate and production of reducing sugars was estimated by Nelson method. Standard curve of glucose (0.1-0.5 μmol) was used in calculation. Amylase (AMY) was assayed (Aggarwal et al., 2021) using starch as substrate and production of reducing sugars was estimated by DNS method. The standard curve of maltose (1-5 μmol) was used in calculation. Sucrose synthase (SuSy) (synthesis) was assayed by using UDP-glucose and fructose as substrates, and sucrose phosphate synthase (SPS) was assayed by using UDP-glucose and fructose-6-phosphate as substrates (Aggarwal et al., 2024).

Production of sucrose was estimated by anthrone based method using sucrose (50- 200 nmol) as standard. SuSy (breakdown) was assayed using sucrose and UDP as substrates, and production of fructose was estimated by Nelson method and amount was calculated by taking fructose (50–200 nmol) as standard. All other enzymes were assayed as mentioned (Aggarwal et al., 2024). Starch phosphorylase (STP) was assayed using starch and Na-Pi (sodium monophosphate salt) as substrates. ADP-glucose pyrophosphorylase (AGPase) was assayed by using sodium tetrapyrophosphate and ADP-glucose as substrates. UDP-glucose pyrophosphorylase (UGPase) was assayed by using sodium tetrapyrophosphate and UDP-glucose as substrates. Glucose-1-phosphate released in these reactions was estimated in NADPH by using phosphoglucomutase and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase. Activity was calculated using molar extinction coefficient of NADPH of 6.22 mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Starch synthase (SS) was estimated by using ADP-glucose and amylopectin as its substrates. Granule bound starch synthase (GBSS) was estimated by using ADP-glucose as its substrate. Released ADP in these reactions was estimated in NADPH by using pyruvate kinase, hexokinase, and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase.

Statistical analysis

Experiments were performed with three biological replicates. Data were subjected to two-factor ANOVA to determine the effects of cultivar and treatment, and their interaction. Data in interaction were analyzed by Fisher's least significant difference at $p < 0.05$. RStudio (ver. 1.4.1717, Boston, MA) was used for statistical analyses.

Results

MDA, protein carbonyls and proteins

MDA (Fig. 1a) increased under desiccation while decreased under rehydration in all cultivars other than PBW644. In PBW644, MDA remained unaltered under desiccation and increased by a small amount under rehydration. The highest MDA was seen in the desiccated state of PBW343 while the least MDA was seen in the desiccated state of PBW644.

Protein carbonyls (Fig. 1b) increased under desiccation in PBW343 only and protein carbonyls increased under rehydration in all cultivars other than PBW343 and in PBW343, protein carbonyls decreased under rehydration. The highest protein carbonyls level was seen in the desiccated state of PBW343 while the least protein carbonyls was seen in the desiccated state of PBW644/C306/Dharwad dry.

Protein content (Fig. 1c) decreased under desiccation in all cultivars other than PBW660 and increased under rehydration in all cultivars. The least protein content was observed in the desiccated state of PBW343 while protein levels were high in the desiccated states of PBW644/C306/Dharwad dry. Protein level was low in the rehydrated state of PBW343 while were high in the rehydrated states of PBW644/C306/Sunstar.

Visual pictures (Fig. 2) showed that seedlings were regrown under rehydration in all cultivars. Results concluded that post-germination DT was superior in other cultivars than PBW343. Further analyses were performed on PBW644 and PBW343 being contrasted in DT.

GABA and proline

GABA and GAD increased under desiccation (50% and 4-fold) while decreased under rehydration (by 60-70%) (Table 1). DAO decreased under desiccation (50-70%) and increased under rehydration (about 3-fold). Proline increased by high amount under desiccation compared to rehydration in both cultivars. Proline increased by more amount in PBW644 (80%) than PBW343 (45%) under

desiccation. GABA and proline levels were higher in PBW644 than PBW343 (20% and 5%) under desiccation.

Fig. 1 Changes of malondialdehyde (MDA) (a) and protein carbonyls (b) and protein (c) during post-germination desiccation and rehydration in seedlings of wheat cv. C306, Dharwad Dry, PBW343, PBW660, Sunstar and PBW644. Values are the mean \pm S.D. Different letters indicated significant difference (Fisher's L. S. D. at $p < 0.05$).

Carbohydrates

SPS, SuSy (synthesis) and SuSy (breakdown) increased under desiccation (70-90%) and rehydration (10-20%). INV and AMY decreased by large amount under desiccation however revived under rehydration. Other carbohydrates enzymatic activities, and contents of sugars and starch were altered by 5-15% under desiccation and increased by 40-80% under rehydration.

SPS, SuSy (synthesis) and SuSy (breakdown) increased by more amount in PBW644, and UGPase, SS, and STP decreased by more amount in PBW343 under desiccation. GBSS decreased in PBW343

only under desiccation. Glucose decreased in PBW343 only, and fructose and starch decreased by more amount in PBW343 under desiccation. However, sucrose decreased by more amount in PBW644 under desiccation.

Fig. 2 Rehydrated seedlings after post-germination desiccation in six wheat cultivars, C 306, Dharwad Dry, PBW660, Sunstar, PBW644 (all five are drought tolerant) and PBW 343 (drought susceptible).

Table 1. GABA, glutamate decarboxylase (GAD), diamine oxidase (DAO) and proline changes during post-germination desiccation and rehydration in wheat cv. PBW644 and PBW343.

Measure	PBW644			PBW343		
	Pre-desiccated	Desiccated	Rehydrated	Pre-desiccated	Desiccated	Rehydrated
GABA ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ DW)	1.18 ^c ±0.03	1.74 ^a ±0.02	0.56 ^e ±0.01	0.99 ^d ±0.02	1.47 ^b ±0.02	0.53 ^e ±0.02
GAD (nkat g^{-1} DW)	11.56 ^c ±0.29	39.4 ^a ±0.26	12.4 ^b ±0.15	10.38 ^d ±0.57	39.33 ^a ±0.14	11.02 ^{cd} ±0.52
DAO units g^{-1} DW	12.95 ^d ±0.53	5.88 ^f ±0.37	15.12 ^c ±0.55	25.35 ^a ±0.58	7.3 ^e ±0.35	18.36 ^b ±0.37
Proline ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ DW)	2.87 ^e ±0.05	5.13 ^b ±0.04	5.66 ^a ±0.13	3.4 ^d ±0.04	4.94 ^c ±0.06	5.59 ^a ±0.09

One DAO unit is defined as the change of absorbance of one in one hour

Values are mean \pm S. D. (n=3)

Different alphabets in a row indicate significant difference (Fisher's L. S. D. at $p < 0.05$)

Table 2. Carbohydrates changes during post-germination desiccation and rehydration in wheat cv. PBW644 and PBW343.

Measure	PBW644			PBW343		
	Pre-desiccated	Desiccated	Rehydrated	Pre-desiccated	Desiccated	Rehydrated
SPS (nkat g^{-1} DW)	96.58 ^a ±0.31	169.55 ^c ±0.46	182.13 ^b ±0.78	94.32 ^f ±0.24	161.1 ^d ±0.56	186.03 ^a ±0.34
SuSy (synthesis) (nkat g^{-1} DW)	89.83 ^a ±0.18	160.17 ^c ±0.46	192.68 ^a ±0.59	87.25 ^f ±0.31	145.75 ^d ±0.32	183.52 ^b ±0.56
SuSy (breakdown) (nkat g^{-1} DW)	255.57 ^f ±0	493.17 ^c ±1.89	590.33 ^a ±0	261.04 ^e ±1.89	474.11 ^d ±1.79	585.34 ^b ±2.41
AGPase (nkat g^{-1} DW)	10.73 ^c ±0.28	10.92 ^c ±0.25	15.26 ^b ±0.25	7.48 ^e ±0.18	7.97 ^d ±0.18	14.29 ^b ±0.33
UGPase (nkat g^{-1} DW)	24.27 ^c ±0.28	22.73 ^d ±0.25	34.65 ^a ±0.25	22.56 ^d ±0.28	20.18 ^e ±0.24	33.4 ^b ±0.33
SS (nkat g^{-1} DW)	68.73 ^d ±0.43	65.21 ^e ±0.53	94.02 ^b ±0.71	71.54 ^c ±0.57	64.89 ^e ±0.49	97.03 ^a ±0.68
GBSS (nkat g^{-1} DW)	3.73 ^e ±0.07	3.62 ^e ±0.06	7.05 ^b ±0.04	4.25 ^c ±0.02	3.96 ^d ±0.07	7.46 ^a ±0.08
STP (nkat g^{-1} DW)	48.51 ^c ±0.37	46.15 ^d ±0.34	58.54 ^a ±0.52	45.63 ^d ±0.78	41.7 ^e ±0.32	56.58 ^b ±0.52
INV (nkat g^{-1} DW)	213.37 ^b ±8.92	0.58 ^e ±0.00	162.76 ^c ±1.66	305.85 ^a ±1.21	6.64 ^d ±0.84	209.33 ^b ±0.83
AMY (nkat g^{-1} DW)	339.23 ^a ±5.77	68.65 ^d ±1.72	292.71 ^b ±1.22	338.3 ^a ±4.35	48.15 ^e ±2.48	271.88 ^c ±2.12
Glc ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ DW)	186.01 ^d ±1.26	184.03 ^d ±1.15	323.33 ^b ±1.42	193.07 ^c ±1.26	176.56 ^e ±1.66	331.21 ^a ±2.17
Fru ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ DW)	360.49 ^c ±0.97	321.03 ^e ±3.19	414.09 ^a ±3.27	353.34 ^d ±4.45	300.19 ^f ±3.84	397.95 ^b ±1.09
Suc ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ DW)	54.41 ^d ±2.19	44.86 ^e ±1.99	84.14 ^a ±2.95	66.46 ^b ±2.91	59.82 ^c ±1.09	86.36 ^a ±1.64
Starch (mg g^{-1} DW)	60.32 ^e ±0.35	57.06 ^e ±0.32	92.97 ^a ±0.34	58.52 ^d ±0.31	52.11 ^f ±0.3	90.79 ^b ±0.53

Values are mean \pm S. D. (n=3)

Different alphabets in a row indicate significant difference (Fisher's L. S. D. at $p < 0.05$)

SPS, sucrose phosphate synthase; SuSy, sucrose synthase; AGPase, ADP-glucose pyrophosphorylase; UGPase, UDP-glucose pyrophosphorylase; SS, soluble starch synthase; GBSS, granule-bound starch synthase; STP, starch phosphorylases; INV, invertase; AMY, amylase; Glc, glucose; Fru, fructose; Suc, sucrose

Antioxidants

Lignin increased under desiccation and rehydration by more amount in PBW644 (46% and 95%) than PBW343 (37% and 82%). Phenolics decreased by less amount in PBW644 (15%) compared to PBW343 (2.4-fold) under desiccation and under rehydration, phenolics increased in PBW343 only. Phenolics level under desiccation was higher in PBW644 than PBW343. Flavonoids increased by almost the same amount (about 30%) in both cultivars under desiccation while under rehydration,

flavonoids increased by more amount in PBW644 (20%) than PBW343 (5%). Anthocyanins increased by more amount in PBW644 (2-fold) than PBW343 (1.4-fold) under desiccation and under rehydration, anthocyanins increased in both cultivars. PPO was unaltered in PBW644 while increased in PBW343 (80%) under desiccation and under rehydration, PPO increased by high amount in PBW644 (3.6-fold) compared to PBW343 (1.6-fold).

POX decreased by less amount in PBW644 (4%) compared to PBW343 (10%) under desiccation while POX increased in both cultivars under rehydration. POX levels remained higher in PBW644 than PBW343 under desiccation and under rehydration. GPX decreased by about 50% in both cultivars under desiccation while under rehydration, GPX increased by a high amount in PBW644 (40%) compared to PBW343 (14%). GPX levels remained higher in PBW644 than PBW343 under desiccation and rehydration. GST decreased by less amount in PBW343 (1.3-fold) compared to PBW644 (2-fold) under desiccation, and under rehydration, GST increased by the same amount in both cultivars (2-fold). GST levels remained higher in PBW343 than PBW644 under desiccation and under rehydration. GSH and GSH/GSSG decreased by high amount in PBW644 (12-fold) compared to PBW343 (1.3-fold and 2-fold) under desiccation, and under rehydration, GSH and GSH/GSSG increased many folds in PBW644 (40-fold and 12-fold) compared to PBW343 (4.4-fold and 2.2-fold). GSSG remained unaltered under desiccation while increased by about 2-3-fold under rehydration in both cultivars. GSSG levels were similar between cultivars under desiccation.

Table 3. Antioxidant changes during post-germination desiccation and rehydration in wheat cv. PBW644 and PBW343

Measure	PBW644			PBW343		
	Pre-desiccated	Desiccated	Rehydrated	Pre-desiccated	Desiccated	Rehydrated
Lignin (mg g ⁻¹ DW)	18.96 ^f ±0.13	27.71 ^c ±0.08	53.94 ^a ±0.18	19.53 ^c ±0.15	26.88 ^d ±0.16	48.99 ^b ±0.25
Phenolics (mg GA equiv. g ⁻¹ DW)	9.44 ^c ±0.056	8.175 ^d ±0.038	7.707 ^e ±0.091	14.562 ^a ±0.087	6.189 ^f ±0.072	11.854 ^b ±0.147
Flavonoids (mg rutin equiv. g ⁻¹ DW)	1.201 ^d ±0.018	1.525 ^e ±0.011	1.805 ^b ±0.021	1.153 ^c ±0.009	1.55 ^c ±0.023	1.627 ^b ±0.008
Anthocyanins (Abs. g ⁻¹ DW)	0.899 ^f ±0.011	1.81 ^c ±0.022	4.562 ^b ±0.025	1.142 ^c ±0.043	1.646 ^d ±0.028	5.007 ^a ±0.02
PPO units g ⁻¹ DW	72.83 ^d ±0.00	85.51 ^d ±4.77	306.91 ^a ±18.5	72.63 ^d ±9.08	130.41 ^e ±4.51	212.92 ^b ±6.95
POX (μkat g ⁻¹ DW)	5.624 ^c ±0.017	5.406 ^d ±0.027	7.027 ^a ±0.000	4.802 ^c ±0.017	4.373 ^f ±0.015	6.267 ^b ±0.04
GPX (nkat g ⁻¹ DW)	60.62 ^a ±4.14	39.73 ^d ±1.42	55.45 ^b ±0.78	51.76 ^c ±1.18	35.81 ^e ±0.51	40.69 ^d ±1.36
GST (nkat g ⁻¹ DW)	682.7 ^d ±0.4	340.7 ^f ±0.6	740.3 ^b ±1.6	719.9 ^c ±0.7	549.3 ^e ±0	1092.5 ^a ±1.92
GSH (μmol g ⁻¹ DW)	3.292 ^c ±0.157	0.27 ^f ±0.046	10.688 ^a ±0.045	2.978 ^d ±0.355	1.496 ^e ±0.029	6.538 ^b ±0.092
GSSG (μmol g ⁻¹ DW)	0.514 ^c ±0.074	0.503 ^c ±0.015	1.632 ^a ±0.045	0.513 ^c ±0.123	0.476 ^c ±0.029	0.926 ^b ±0.046
GSH/GSSG ratio	6.47 ^a ±0.724	0.534 ^c ±0.077	6.552 ^a ±0.214	5.988 ^a ±1.3	3.152 ^b ±0.22	7.071 ^a ±0.419

Values are mean ± S. D. (n=3)

Different alphabets in a row indicate significant difference (Fisher's L. S. D. at p < 0.05)

PPO, polyphenol oxidase; POX, peroxidase; GPX, glutathione peroxidase; GST, glutathione-S-transferase; GSH, reduced glutathione; GSSG, oxidised glutathione

One PPO unit is defined as the change of absorbance of one in one hour

Discussion

Present study indicated that oxidative toxicity level of desiccated state can be used as marker for drought tolerance. The current investigation revealed that post-germination DT was superior in drought tolerant cultivars compared to the drought susceptible cultivar. H₂O₂-scavenging can be one of the essential factors related to DT. Catalase and ascorbate were the critical antioxidants in seed-DT (Bailly et al., 2004; Ishibashi et al., 2008). Peroxidases and catalase were involved in the extreme drought tolerance of *Selaginella tamariscina* compared to drought sensitive *Selaginella moellendorffii* (Gu et al., 2019). The present study related peroxidases and glutathione peroxidases to the superior DT of PBW644. GSTs were induced under toxicity, and products of oxidative damages can be the inducers of detoxification (Gapińska et al., 2008; Halusková et al., 2009; Kaur et al., 2014). The present study found extents of GST in the desiccated state of PBW343 compared to PBW644.

Phenolics, flavonoids and anthocyanins have been pinpointed to be the powerful antioxidants involved under desiccation (Gu et al., 2019; Bentley et al., 2019). Phenolics dropped while PPO activity escalated upon desiccation in PBW343, which conveyed that phenolics were utilized by PPO to control overly produced oxidative stress in the desiccated state of PBW343. Present study related lignin during desiccation and rehydration with superior DT of PBW644. Lignin deposition in the cell

walls may prevent water loss during desiccation (Gechev et al., 2021). Cell walls of desiccation tolerant resurrection plants have been advised to withstand extreme mechanical stress upon dehydration and rehydration (Chen et al., 2020). The current investigation described that GAD activity was linked to generate GABA under desiccation. Curtailed DAO specified that diamines probably were diverted towards polyamine synthesis under desiccation (Wang et al., 2022). Overactive GAD may alter carbon to nitrogen ratio and cause cell death (Michaeli and Fromm, 2015) and the present analysis found that GAD is enhanced under desiccation while fall off upon rehydration. Simultaneous accumulation of GABA and proline under desiccation stated that both molecules may be important for survival (Signorelli et al., 2015). The elevation of proline (Oliver et al., 2011; Yobi et al., 2019) and GABA (Sugiyama et al., 2014) in response to desiccation have been reported in resurrection plants.

Sucrose and UDP-glucose produced by sucrose synthase and sucrose phosphate synthase may be directed towards the synthesis of raffinose series oligosaccharides, and cell wall components. Sucrose decreased with high effect in PBW644 under desiccation and thus may be directed towards the formation of myo-inositol, raffinose series oligosaccharides (Pandey et al., 2010). The present study found that PBW644 switched GSH between desiccation and rehydration. Gamma-glutamyl might be transferred from GSH to amino acids for stable amino acid storage under desiccation (Oliver et al., 2011; Yobi et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2021) while during rehydration, GSH was regenerated. The present study found that amylases and invertases were inhibited, however starch phosphorylase continued during desiccation. Starch phosphorylase might be preferred over amylase under desiccation because reducing sugars produced by amylase may be detrimental to desiccated tissues (Oliver et al., 2011). Starch synthetic activities due to ADP-glucose pyrophosphorylase and starch synthase continued during desiccation which indicated that starch might be preserved as reserve. Sugar-starch interconversions have been reported to play an important role in tolerance of the plants towards stresses (reviewed by Dong and Beckles, 2019).

Conclusion

The present study concluded that antioxidant activity plays a pivotal role under post-germination desiccation and rehydration in wheat. H_2O_2 -scavenging may have a key role in desiccation and rehydration. Secondary antioxidants of non-enzymatic (phenolics, flavonoids and anthocyanins) and enzymatic (polyphenol oxidases and peroxidases) origins may play salient roles under desiccation and rehydration. Sucrose and UDP-glucose produced through the activities of sucrose synthase and sucrose phosphate synthase may be utilized to synthesize protective raffinose oligosaccharides and cell wall components under desiccation. Energy conservation may be the mode of survival by turning down major catabolic activities by invertase, amylase and diamine oxidase under desiccation. Starch may serve as the principal source of energy, and enzymes of starch metabolism continue to work to provide precursors for the synthesis of stress protectants and energy under desiccation. Glutamate decarboxylase produces GABA under desiccation. Lignin deposition may play important roles in desiccation and rehydration.

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Author Contributions

PS: acquisition of data, data analysis, data interpretation. VKZ: conception, design, data analysis, data interpretation, and drafting the article. JS: conception, design, and drafting the article.

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